

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Correlation and Regression Analysis of the Laws of Change in Water Consumption in Economic Sectors

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Annotation.

In this work, the state of water resource use in the conditions of the region and their distribution in the main sectors of the economy were analyzed. Using correlation and regression models, the degree of interdependence and forces of influence of water consumption in the context of economic sectors were assessed. The obtained results make it possible to effectively manage water resources, their optimal distribution, and determine promising directions. The research results can be used to analyze the current state of rational use of water resources and water consumption by industry, as well as to assess the possibilities of optimal distribution in the future.

Keywords: regression analysis, regression methods, correlation index, determination index.

Introduction

The efficient and rational use of water resources is closely linked to agriculture, industry, energy, and the standard of living of the population. Therefore, the development of models for the effective distribution and management of water consumption in the context of economic sectors is relevant. This is especially important for long-term planning, increasing production efficiency, and reducing environmental risks in conditions of water scarcity.

In several scientific sources, correlation and regression methods are widely used to determine the relationship between water consumption and economic growth indicators. The relationship between such indicators as water consumption, gross domestic product, population, and production volume is analyzed, and the possibility of forecasting trends in the use of water resources in the future is created [?, ?, ?]. The possibility of using correlation and regression analysis for forecasting the gross regional product was studied in [4]. Mathematical and informational methods of effective forecasting of water resource consumption were studied in [5].

Literature analysis and methodology

In this work [6], the application of correlation methods for analyzing the patterns of changes in water consumption and water use in economic sectors is considered. Indicators

of water resource use in the sectors of the economy of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are shown in Figure 1.

1) Irrigation

Irrigation accounts for 95.73% of the total volume of water resources in the republic. Based on the data from sources [7], [8], [9], and in accordance with the adopted methodology, a correlation dependence model is developed. The correlation analysis is conducted using statistical data for the period 2007–2023, as presented below.

As a result of calculations, the linear regression equation is

$$y \approx -21.28x + 6943.28,$$

with the correlation index $R \approx -0.0582$ and the determination index $R^2 \approx 0.003$. The graph of the regression equation is shown in Figure 1.2a.

The quadratic regression equation is

$$y = -38.0433x^2 + 663.4989x + 4774.8204,$$

with the correlation index $R \approx 0.4569$ and the determination index $R^2 \approx 0.2087$. The graph of the regression equation is shown in Figure 1.2b.

The cubic regression equation is

$$y = -3.6139x^3 + 59.5324x^2 - 59.2838x + 6010.7788,$$

with the correlation index $R \approx 0.492$ and the determination index $R^2 \approx 0.2421$. The graph of the regression equation is shown in Figure 1.2c.

Figure 1.2.a. Graph of the equation of linear regression of changes in water use in irrigation

Figure 1.2.v. Quadratic regression equation graph of changes in water use in irrigation

Figure 1.2.c. Graph of the cubic regression equation of changes in water use in irrigation

2) Industry

Industry accounts for **0.42%** of the total volume of water resources of the republic. According to Table 1 [4:1-25], and in accordance with the adopted methodology, a correlation dependence model is developed. The correlation analysis is carried out using statistical data for the period **2007–2023**, as follows:

As a result of calculations, the linear regression equation is

$$y \approx 0.0368x + 5.1868,$$

with the correlation index $R \approx 0.559$ and the determination index $R^2 \approx 0.3125$. The graph of the regression equation is shown in Figure 1.3a.

The quadratic regression equation is

$$y = 0.0084x^2 - 0.1142x + 5.6647,$$

with the correlation index $R \approx 0.7883$ and the determination index $R^2 \approx 0.6213$. The graph of the regression equation is shown in Figure 1.3b.

The cubic regression equation is

$$y = 0.0015x^3 - 0.0322x^2 + 0.1868x + 5.15,$$

with the correlation index $R \approx 0.8947$ and the determination index $R^2 \approx 0.8004$. The graph of the regression equation is shown in Figure 1.3c.

Figure 1.3.a. Graph of the linear regression equation of changes in industrial water use

Figure 1.3.v. Quadratic regression equation graph of changes in industrial water

Figure 1.3.c. Graph of the cubic regression equation of changes in industrial water use

3) Utilities

Utilities account for **2.35%** of the total volume of water resources of the republic. According to Table 1 [4:1-25], and in accordance with the adopted methodology, a correlation dependence model is developed. The correlation analysis is carried out using statistical data for the period **2007–2023**, as follows:

As a result of calculations, the linear regression equation is

$$y = 1.4282x + 149.9185,$$

with the correlation index $R \approx 0.8021$ and the determination index $R^2 \approx 0.6434$. The graph of the regression equation is shown in Figure 1.4a.

The quadratic regression equation is

$$y = 0.0057x^2 + 1.3265x + 150.2406,$$

with the correlation index $R \approx 0.8022$ and the determination index $R^2 \approx 0.6436$. The graph of the regression equation is shown in Figure 1.4b.

Figure 1.4.a. Graph of the equation of linear regression of changes in the use of municipal water

Figure 1.4.c. Graph of the quadratic regression equation of changes in water use in the utilities sector

Figure 1.4.c. Graph of the cubic regression equation of changes in water use in the utilities sector

The cubic regression equation is

$$y = 0.0037x^3 - 0.0955x^2 + 2.0759x + 148.9591,$$

with the correlation index $R \approx 0.8032$ and the determination index $R^2 \approx 0.6451$. The graph of the regression equation is shown in Figure 1.4c.

4) Energy

The energy sector accounts for **3.85%** of the total volume of water resources of the republic. According to Table 1 [4:1-25], and in accordance with the adopted methodology, a correlation dependence model is developed. The correlation analysis is carried out using statistical data for the period **2007–2023**, as follows:

As a result of calculations, the linear regression equation is

$$y \approx -1.9945x + 289.7804,$$

with the correlation index $R \approx -0.1604$ and the determination index $R^2 \approx 0.0257$. The graph of the regression equation is shown in Figure 1.5a.

The quadratic regression equation is

$$y = -0.8119x^2 + 12.6199x + 243.5016,$$

with the correlation index $R \approx 0.3268$ and the determination index $R^2 \approx 0.1068$. The graph of the regression equation is shown in Figure 1.5b.

The cubic regression equation is

$$y = 0.055x^3 - 2.2971x^2 + 23.6216x + 224.6887,$$

with the correlation index $R \approx 0.3369$ and the determination index $R^2 \approx 0.1135$. The graph of the regression equation is shown in Figure 1.5c.

Figure 1.5.a. Graph of the linear regression equation of changes in water use in the energy sector

Figure 1.5.v. Quadratic regression equation graph of changes in energy water use

Figure 1.5.c. Graph of cubic regression equation of changes in energy water use

5) Fishery

Fishery accounts for **1.36%** of the total volume of water resources of the republic. According to Table 1 (4)[4:-25], and in accordance with the adopted methodology, a correlation dependence model is developed. The correlation analysis is carried out using statistical data for the period **2007–2023**, as follows:

As a result of calculations, the linear regression equation is

$$y = 4.9265x + 51.8121,$$

with the correlation index $R \approx 0.2102$ and the determination index $R^2 \approx 0.0442$. The graph of the regression equation is shown in Figure 1.6a.

The quadratic regression equation is

$$y = 1.04x^2 - 13.7943x + 111.0947,$$

with the correlation index $R \approx 0.2857$ and the determination index $R^2 \approx 0.0816$. The graph of the regression equation is shown in Figure 1.6b.

The cubic regression equation is

$$y = 0.5793x^3 - 14.601x^2 + 102.0656x - 87.0257,$$

with the correlation index $R \approx 0.3806$ and the determination index $R^2 \approx 0.2906$. The graph of the regression equation is shown in Figure 1.6c.

Figure 1.6.a. Graph of the linear regression equation of changes in water use in fisheries

Figure 1.6.b. Graph of the quadratic regression equation of changes in water use in fisheries

Figure 1.6.c. Graph of the cubic regression equation of changes in water use in fisheries

Consideration

Based on these calculations, the following discussion is conducted on the assessment of the correlation index and determination index: -sectors of the economy - housing and communal services and industry. It is proven that water consumption and water use are constant in relation to the water level of the year, and the regression equation calculated for them has a correlation index $R \geq 0.5$ and $R^2 \geq 0.5$ a determination index.

As can be seen from Table 1, R has negative and positive values. Negative values represent a decrease in water consumption and water use in the republic, while positive values represent an increase. It can be seen that the total water consumption of the republic in irrigation decreases, while in other sectors of the economy it increases. For further confirmation of this data, it will be necessary to organize regular measurements of accurate calculations of water resources used by rivers, reservoirs, and other water bodies that provide water resources to economic sectors. The presence of a correlation index of the linear regression equation, calculated during the analysis of changes in water consumption and water use in the irrigation and energy sectors and regression assessments, represents a decrease $R < 0$ in water consumption and water use.

Results

The results of regression calculations for these sectors of the economy are presented in Table 1.

**Table 1. Results of regression calculations by sectors of the economy
(Correlation index R and determination index R^2)**

Fields of economy	Linear regression		Quadratic regression		Cubic regression		Conclusion
	R	R^2	R	R^2	R	R^2	
Irrigation	-0.058	0.003	0.456	0.208	0.492	0.242	Decrease in water consumption has a tendency
Industry	0.559	0.3125	0.7883	0.6213	0.890	0.800	Increase in water consumption There is a tendency
Public utilities	0.802	0.643	0.802	0.643	0.803	0.645	Sustainable growth trend
Energy	-0.160	0.025	0.320	0.106	0.330	0.110	No intrinsic connection and water consumption has a downward trend
Fishing	0.210	0.040	0.280	0.080	0.380	0.290	Weak bond

Conclusion

The following conclusions can be drawn from this research:

- The largest share of water consumption is attributed to irrigation; however, in recent years, a downward trend in water consumption has been observed.
- Water consumption in the industrial and utilities sectors demonstrates a clear upward trend.
- No stable relationship is identified in water consumption within the energy sector and fisheries; consequently, sharp fluctuations may occur depending on the level of water availability.

In general, the efficient allocation of water resources requires reliance on scientifically grounded statistical and economic models.

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